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**INVESTIGATING THE THERMAL QUALITIES OF BIOCOMPOSITE LIGNIN
FOAM PRODUCED FROM *Arenga pinnata* (KAONG) FRUIT WASTE WITH
NON-TOXIC ADDITIVES**

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of the Requirements for the Degree
Bachelor of Science in Biology

**KYLA MARIE DOLORICON
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COLLEGE OF ALLIED MEDICAL SCIENCES

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**INVESTIGATING THE THERMAL QUALITIES OF BIOCOMPOSITE LIGNIN
FOAM PRODUCED FROM *ARENGA PINNATA* (KAONG) FRUIT WASTE
WITH NON-TOXIC ADDITIVES**

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ABSTRACT

Polyurethane foams are versatile materials favored for their multiple industrial uses. However, these foams are plastic, conventionally derived from non-renewable and non-biodegradable petrochemicals. Studies have addressed this by partly or wholly replacing petrol with lignin, a renewable biopolymer. Yan et al. (2024) produced pure, rigid lignin foams from kraft lignin via cold press and baking, the results focusing on how moisture level affects morphology and porosity. However, the resultant foams faced brittleness and fragility issues.

Through their methods, this study focused on biocomposite kaong-lignin foams with varying moisture levels of 1.2, 1.4, and 1.6 mL and how they influence thermal resistance, conductivity, and density, coupled with non-toxic additives to reduce rigidity. Kaong fruit shells and stalks in equal parts were ground and fractionated through choline chloride:lactic acid DES methods. After washing, a gravimetric analysis of purity revealed 55% ethanol solubility, interpreted as lignin. The entire extracted DES lignin was combined with PVA, starch, and glycerin to enhance morphology. Sample moisture levels of 0, 1.2, 1.4, and 1.6 mL per total sample volume were molded and baked at 10 degrees celsius/minute up to 240 degrees celsius and cooled to room temperature. The experimental samples were weighed and tested for thermal values through the hot plate method.

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Results showed that the 1.4 mL sample resulted as the foam with the highest resistance to heat, lowest conductivity, and lowest density. Additionally, it was found to be the non-significant sample compared to positive control in thermal resistance, possibly indicating comparable performance. All foams demonstrated inherent insulation properties relative to the negative control. Density analysis revealed significant differences compared to standard PUF but not relative to the 0 mL kaong foam.

This research highlights the thermal capabilities of DES kaong-lignin foam formed with eco-friendly approaches and materials, combating petrol derivation without compromising intrinsic foam qualities.

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Chapter I
INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Polyurethane foams (PUF) are flexible materials, with properties ranging from soft touch coatings to rock-hard, rigid, construction materials. Since they are light, good insulators and resilient in nature, they are utilized in multiple fields, such as buildings, automotive, furniture, and packaging (Das & Mahanwar, 2020). PUFs are typically manufactured with polyols derived from petrochemicals, which are limited in supply and non-renewable. With its negative impact on the environment, there is a rising interest in making polyurethane-based foam less reliant on fossil fuels by adding renewable, sustainable materials. A contender for a predominant, synthetic chemical replacement in foam-making is lignin, the second most abundant biopolymer after cellulose. While many studies have employed the use of lignin as a partial substitute, with varying methods, additives, purpose, and materials (Han et al., 2025), a few studies have also successfully and fully replaced synthetic polyols with lignin (Yan et al., 2024). However, as discovered by the same researchers, full lignin foams were inherently fragile, their porosity was sensitive to moisture, and there were tradeoffs between density and insulation.

Lignin is a renewable, aromatic polymer found in biomass which is a component that supports plant structure. Due to its structural integrity, rigidity, and abundance, successful studies have been conducted with the examination of the partial and full replacement of synthetic polyols with lignin instead as biopolyols. Moreover, the studies concerning PUFs with lignin observed additional advantages such as improved thermal stability, rigidity, and biodegradability (Shafiq et

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al., n.d.). In the study by Yan et al. (2024), commercial foam products were compared to the 100% lignin foam they produced. The density and compressive strength of the resultant foams exhibited higher values than those of polystyrene foams, and are comparable to phenolic-based PUFs. This makes lignin-based foams not only more environmentally friendly, but industrially better compared to standard foams.

The full replacement of synthetic polyols with lignin-polyol (still including standard foam making chemicals) is impractical due to tradeoffs between performance, solubility, and flexibility. It is a domain that is experimental, heavily controlled, and relatively underexplored. Nevertheless, the full replacement of all rigid foam-making chemicals with only lignin and water was possible, as shown in the study by Yan and other researchers, which produced rigid, open-cell lignin foams (Bernardini et al., n.d.; Gondaliya & Nejad, 2021; Zieglowski et al., 2019). Despite these concerns, it remains significant. The environmental impact of PUF manufacturing is reduced by simply partially or wholly replacing petrol-derived polyols, all without compromising the industrial properties of traditional PUFs (Vieira et al., 2023). Therefore, there is value in understanding the insulating properties of lignin-based foams.

Arenga pinnata, known in the Philippines as Kaong, is a sugar palm tree known for its sweet, chewy fruit that is translucent white in color. The Kaong Capital of the Philippines is Indang, Cavite, where the plant grows abundantly, either voluntarily or purposely planted in the riverbanks. In a study, its lignin content was examined, and is found to range around 21%-46%, depending on the part and method. The most widely cited literature for its lignin content calculated the dry weight to be about 46.44%, making its trunk the lignin-richest part. Other

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constituents like the bunch and processed fibers retained figures of around 14-27% (Papa, 2021; Aisyadea et al., 2023; Hakim et al., 2024). However, in another study, the sugar palm trunk waste was reported at 33.24% (Erliana et al., 2020). Meanwhile, the bunch waste contained a decent amount of lignin, ranging around 27.23% (Hakim, 2024).

One of the bases of this research, titled Eco-foaming Lignin for Innovative Rigid Foam, produced rigid lignin foams via technical kraft lignin from an unspecified, woody biomass source. This study explored the potential of kaong fruit waste, an underutilized source of lignin, as a lignin foam, extracted through a milder method termed as deep eutectic solvent extraction. This study also confronted the issues with pure lignin foams, by incorporating non-toxic additives. PVA was crucial for structural stability, glycerin for plasticizing and reducing brittleness, and starch as a filler and co-binder. Their ease of use, inexpensiveness, and non-toxic nature made them valuable additives for the goals of this study (Wang et al., 2023; Sajjadi & Zakaria, 2023).

Despite the examination of its lignin content, kaong remains greatly underutilized for its lignin. Although there is no direct mention of lignin DES extraction in that plant species specifically, there is research that investigated the feasibility of extracting lignin from kaong fiber for packaging purposes (Syahidah et al., 2025). However, some structurally similar plants like oil palm have used DES for lignin extraction, serving a promising approach for kaong lignin extraction (Arfat et al. 2024).

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In the study by Yan et al. (2024), kraft lignin was used, which when derived from black liquor is toxic, as previously stated (Han et al., 2025). To be consistent with sustainability and environmentally friendly goals, this was addressed through lignin acquisition from *Arenga pinnata* waste in its raw form, and was processed instead through DES extraction, an environmentally friendly alternative to black liquor lignin fractionation (Alam et al., 2024; Magalhães et al., 2024). To combat the brittleness, fragility, and sensitivity of pure lignin foams, the non-toxic additives PVA, starch (cornstarch), and pure glycerin were incorporated, following the green goals of the study.

The study by Yan et al. (2024) lightly covered the thermal conductivity of the resultant foams. Similarly, this study attempted to measure the thermal conductivity, thermal resistance, and density of the resultant foams due to their large presence in insulation, but with DES biocomposite lignin kaong foam with non-toxic additives through feasible methods.

Water or moisture as a blowing agent was a significant component in building the original research, with its different concentrations affecting the covered properties in cellular, physical, and mechanical areas. As a result, the thermal resistance and conductivity values were influenced. Lastly, kaong DES lignin is unique, and is not directly mentioned as a component in foam making in published studies. This study builds on the original by comparing the resulting thermal conductivity and resistance values, and density in each kaong DES lignin foam with varying water level concentrations, of which some values are exclusive in the original study (Yan et al., 2024).

Statement of the Problem

The purpose of this experimental quantitative study is to determine whether there's a statistically significant difference in the thermal resistance, thermal conductivity, and density values of biocomposite kaong-lignin foams and varying water content percentages.

Specifically, the study aimed to answer the following problems:

1. What are the thermal resistance values of biocomposite kaong-lignin foams composed of 50% stalk and 50% fruit shell with the following water content compared to 0 mL (negative control) and conventional PUF (positive control):
 - 1.1. 1.2 mL
 - 1.2. 1.4 mL, and
 - 1.3. 1.6?

2. What are the thermal conductivity values of biocomposite kaong-lignin foams composed of 50% stalk and 50% fruit shell with the following water content compared to 0 mL (negative control) and conventional PUF (positive control):
 - 1.1. 1.2 mL
 - 1.2. 1.4 mL, and
 - 1.3. 1.6 mL?

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3. What are the density values of biocomposite kaong-lignin foams composed of 50% stalk and 50% fruit shell with the following water content compared to 0 mL (negative control) and conventional PUF (positive control):
 - 1.1. 1.2 mL
 - 1.2. 1.4 mL, and
 - 1.3. 1.6 mL?
4. Is there a significant difference in the thermal resistance values of biocomposite kaong-lignin foams and varying water percentages?
5. Is there a significant difference in thermal conductivity values of biocomposite kaong-lignin foams and varying water percentages?
6. Is there a significant difference in the density values of biocomposite kaong-lignin foams and varying water percentages?

Significance of the Study

The objective of this study was to formulate rigid, open-celled foams in an eco-friendly manner based on DES biocomposite lignin sourced from kaong fruit waste, with non-toxic additives to enhance structural stability. The beneficiaries of this study are the following: the local environment, the Philippine foam industry, kaong farmers, foam consumers, and scientific researchers. Its multiple benefits and relevance within different and broad domains will be discussed specifically in the next paragraphs.

With the negative impact of petrol and black liquor on the environment, the untapped potential of kaong lignin using DES produces an opportunity for green foam production in the Philippines. As an extremely abundant and a renewable resource, replacing petrol-based and synthetic chemicals with lignin achieves sustainability. Omitting black liquor lignin fractionation reduces toxic pollutants. More importantly, the lignin will be derived from the waste of the sugar palm tree, *Arenga pinnata*.

Turning kaong waste into eco-friendly foam would benefit the Philippine foam industry. Resultant foams are proven to exhibit comparable and sometimes superior structural, mechanical and thermal properties to commercial foam. This presents not just a green opportunity, but an economical one.

Local kaong farmers would benefit from the foam market, creating a purpose for the waste they used to discard without affecting fruit quantity and quality. It would be converted into a valuable and unique product. This promotes stability in the food as well as the foam industry.

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The improved and comparable quality of the resultant foam would be experienced by the users that test it. As previously mentioned, lignin-based foams are reported to have comparable or superior qualities to conventional foam depending on the quality described. Flame retardancy and antimicrobial properties are unique in lignin-based foams, providing additional benefits on top of the sustainable and eco-friendly product produced.

Integrating kaong waste with DES lignin for the purpose of making rigid foam is a unique endeavor, with multiple areas that are unexplored. This study promotes curiosity for future learners to study a unique domain. Scientific researchers such as biologists, biology students, botanists, material and polymer chemists, environmental scientists, and agricultural researchers would benefit due to the study's relevance in their different disciplines.

Scope and Limitations

The study focused on the thermal resistance of DES biocomposite foam from the waste of *Arenga pinnata* (Kaong). The thermal resistance, thermal conductivity, and density values were the main focus. The lignin was derived strictly from the bunch waste of *Arenga pinnata* through deep eutectic solvents for extraction. The study solely focused on comparing the thermal conductivity and insulation of the resultant foam, with regards to the following varied water content or moisture level of 1.2, 1.4, and 1.6 mL, as well as with 0 moisture and standard rigid foams. Another limit of the study was the purity of DES extraction due to an existing alternative testing of purity via gravimetric analysis (Rashid et al., 2022). Due to various constraints in time, yield, and expenses of extracting pure lignin from the rest of the biomass, the non-lignin

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constituent comprising the total extracted DES lignin was included, hence, the study referred to the foam as a biocomposite foam instead of a pure, rigid, lignin foam.

Only insulation regarding thermal resistance and conductivity were assessed, fire resistance values were not considered. Kraft lignin method from the model study was not followed, only DES kaong lignin was used. Other modification methods for the derived lignin were not explored. Biodegradability and other long-term environmental concerns were not considered due to the limited duration of the thesis.

Chapter II
REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This chapter contains a compilation of studies and literature related to the subject of this periodical paper as well as methods and similar products. The studies stated in this part will be in support of confirming this study.

Lignin-Based Biocomposite Foams

Generally, standard foams like rigid polyurethane foams are renowned for their effectiveness in insulation, preferred in construction, automotive, home appliances, and in many other industries. Characterized from other types of urethane foams due to their rigidity, they provide excellent thermal insulation performance (Sahin, 2024). However, RPUFs (rigid polyurethane foams) rely on petrochemicals which are synthetic, unbiodegradable, and toxic to produce.

An enticing alternative to petrochemicals is lignin, the basis of LBB (lignin-based biocomposite) foams. Lignin is a component found in plant cell walls and has been studied rigorously due to its abundance, biodegradability, as well as its potential in improving multiple intrinsic foam qualities. Recent reviews highlight modifications of lignin, enabling better bonding and dispersion in polymer matrices like PVA to enhance mechanical and thermal strength (Fazeli et al., 2023).

While lignin based foams and polyurethane foams differ greatly according to production and source, they remain similar in terms of their role in insulation. This makes them appropriate counterparts of each other for comparison in testing.

Green Techniques for Lignin Extraction

Lignin is a part of lignocellulose, a polymer found in plant cell walls, the second most abundant natural polymer in the world. Commonly, it is a byproduct of the pulp and paper and ethanol industry. Because of its environmentally friendly profile, affordability, abundance, low density, and biodegradability, it possesses high potential as a resource for biodegradable products. To tap into this potential, aside from employing the considered waste by-product of the pulp and paper industry, thousands of studies have resulted in extracting it, a technique known as lignin extraction or lignin fractionation methods. However, conventional lignin extraction methods rely on significant energy as well as unsustainable practices, leading to disposal problems due to the toxicity of unwanted chemicals produced in the process.

The study by Yan et al. (2024) formulated rigid, open-cell lignin foams using kraft lignin, which is typically extracted via black liquor acid precipitation. Black liquor, which holds lignin in its solution, is a highly toxic compound and contains pollutants that are defiant to biodegradation. While isolating lignin through this process is feasible and common, it impacts the environment negatively. Other fractionation methods including soda and sulfite pumping for lignin extraction are widely used, but still pose environmental concerns due to the release of sulfur dioxide in the process.

To combat this, sustainable and effective methods for lignin extraction are being developed, promoting the shift towards sustainability and bio-friendly practices. Several of these processes are known as *organosolv* technique, supercritical fluid, non-thermal plasma, ionic liquids, deep eutectic solvents, and microwave assisted extraction. Each technique varies in terms

of purity, selectivity, simplicity, time, yield, etc. Though deep eutectic solvent (DES) yield lignin typically contain impurities and DES-based lignin biocomposite foams require additives to improve mechanical integrity, the deep eutectic solvent method remains a favorable technique for the study due to its feasibility, simplicity, effectiveness, and inexpensiveness (Alam et al., 2024; Mariana et al., 2021).

DES Lignin Extraction from a Kaong Relative

The use of deep eutectic solvents for the fractionation of lignin is increasing due to their environmental-friendly profile, as well as their effectiveness in separating lignin from biomass through dissolution. DES are strongly resistant to heat, have a low tendency to evaporate, low in toxicity, and break down naturally, serving as an appealing alternative to traditional biomass lignin fractionation methods (Alam et al., 2024).

Arenga pinnata, a member of the family *Arecaceae*, is not recorded as a biomass that has been used for DES lignin fractionation. Nevertheless, the coconut tree (*Cocos nucifera*) from the same family is recorded as a biomass that has been tested with the DES method. A specially formulated alkaline-DES is used to obtain lignin efficiently and successfully from coconut shells in the study by He et al. (2024). Another study by Zheng et al. (2025) has used acidic DES (choline chloride and lactic acid) with coconut fiber and successfully extracted a lignin yield of 68.5%. The study by Mankar et al. (2021) used the same chemicals (ChCl:LA) but through microwave assisted extraction, achieving stellar lignin yields ranging around 82% and >95% purity from coconut coir.

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According to 2 studies, DES extracted lignin typically shows high thermal stability because of increased branching and condensed aromatic structures formed during the process. In a thermogravimetric analysis, it is shown that the resultant lignin remains thermally stable at elevated structures. The DES lignin resists degradation up to 350 degrees celsius and higher, proving suitable for thermal insulation (Song et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2022). Moreover, the DES method is known for its preservation of native-like lignin linkages as well as functional groups associated with enhanced thermal resistance. Lower molecular weight fractions from DES lignin routinely showed improved antioxidant properties, aiding in durability in thermal applications (Wang et al., 2020; Mao et al., 2023).

A notable property of lignin is its high solubility in ethanol, specifically in aqueous ethanol mixtures ranging around 50-70% concentrations. A reliable study produced by Yuxuan et al. (2022) explored the optimization of an ethanol-based process extraction. The details of weighing the extracts before and after ethanol reflux extraction and drying was documented, allowing the calculation of exact yield and purity via gravimetric methods. With this protocol, ethanol-based gravimetric analysis was performed in this study to calculate the purity of the produced DES lignin extract (Rashid et al., 2022).

Overview of Kaong Lignin

Arenga pinnata or kaong is notorious for its various uses in the industry and food production. Its general chemical composition as reviewed by Sahari et al. (2014) is as follows: 31-70% cellulose, 10-25% hemicellulose, and 7-26% lignin. In another study by Chalid et al. (2015), the sugar palm ijuk fiber has 28.32% lignin, 51.44% cellulose, and 23.88% hemicellulose, which aligns with other related studies. (Mukhtar et al., 2016; Syahidah et al., 2025)

Lignin in the sugar palm tree is reported to be moderate at the bunch, which will be used in the methodology of this study due to its availability as a waste product of food production. In another study, it is reported that the ijuk also contains a decent amount of lignin, up to 28-32% (Mukhtar et al., 2016; Syahidah et al., 2025). Due to this, other studies have explored the potential of its lignin from ijuk in thermoplastic/thermoset matrices for the production of bio-composites like biofilm and biopolymers (Zadeh et al., 2018; Asyraf et al., 2022; Hasan et al., 2025).

Although there are no existing studies exploring the potential of DES kaong lignin, other similar plant species aside from the coconut tree like oil palm are noted for their role in DES extraction. A study extracted oil palm lignin from its biomass through pressurized inert conditions using oxalic acid and choline chloride. Another study explored the potential of lignin from oil palm biomass through deep eutectic solvents as a carbon fiber precursor (Arfat et al., 2024; Sazali et al., 2023). These studies back up the potential of *Arenga pinnata* DES lignin, a similar plant species.

DES Kaong Lignin in Baking Foaming Method

While the biomass used in the study by Yan et al., (2024) was non-specified and in kraft lignin form, the incorporation of kaong DES lignin into the study remained favorable due to multiple reasons. DES lignin is extracted via green solvents, with minimal structure degradation, leading to higher purity and preserved native-like structures (Li & Takkellapati, 2018; Li et al., 2024).

Due to its biodegradable, non-toxic, and reusable solvents, it is more environmentally friendly, unlike the kraft process. In terms of function, there is better solubility in DES lignin, it retains more reactive functional groups unlike kraft lignin, which is relatively less reactive, toxic due to high alkalinity, sulfur, and resistance to biodegradation (Zhao et al., 2019; Younesi-Kordkheili & Pizzi, 2022; Fu et al., 2022). Moreover, kaong DES lignin is unique and sourced from fruit waste, a sustainable, eco-friendly, and abundant candidate for green lignin extraction.

While pure lignin was used in the Yan et al. (2024) study, this study incorporated the entire aqueous layer which had mostly lignin (measured at 55% solubility), as well as other constituents insoluble in ethanol due to limitations in yield and efficiency in time and expense. Biocomposite foams generally have a higher variability which may impact uniformity in cell structure, but are easier to process and have a higher yield (Wang et al., 2024).

Challenges of Pure Lignin Foams and the Role of Additives

Pure lignin foams are relatively understudied compared to lignin-based foams. In the study by Yan et al. who produced pure, rigid lignin foams, the resultant foams are mechanically rigid and fragile. Pure lignin foams tend to be brittle, solid, and crumbly due to their rigid aromatic structure. To combat this, plasticizers and polymers like glycerin, starch, and PVA have been incorporated into the mix to reduce negative qualities.

Glycerin is widely used for its property as a plasticizer in both PUFs and lignin-based foams. It acts through the modification of foam precursors, improving their flexibility, expansion, and cell structure. This results in the reduction of brittleness, a quality characteristic of lignin-based foams. Furthermore, glycerol enhances other properties like flexibility, thermal stability, and biodegradability due to its plasticizing nature, extending chains in different foam polymer matrices like polyester and starch-based foams (Li et al., 2024).

Meanwhile, starch, another common additive of lignin-based foams, can act with PVA or polyvinyl alcohol to enhance lignin in both composite and plastic formulations. Starch is a biodegradable and inexpensive additive known for its film-forming properties attributable to its polysaccharide nature, while PVA optimizes flexibility, mechanical strength, and film-forming via hydrogen bonding with lignin and starch. Their combined approach improves the performance of lignin-based biodegradable plastics and by extension, foams by reducing fragility, enhancing pliability, and enhancing stabilization. Composites produced from both additives are observed to have improved foam qualities like thermal stability, water resistance, and other mechanical properties (Fazeli et al., 2024; Alang et al., 2023). The study by Yan et al. (2021) that produced

the same pure lignin foams also utilized moisture or water as a blowing agent, helping the matrix foam.

Composite Foam Processing: Baking and Cold Pressing Methods

Advanced alternative processing approaches for LBB foams such as baking and cold pressing aid in foam compaction, crosslinking, and density control. Baking promotes polymer matrix consolidation, while cold pressing reduces air voids and increases structural strength. These steps are crucial for the conversion of brittle lignin foams into tougher, cohesive, biocomposite foams appropriate for insulation and other applications (Olazabal-Ticona et al., 2025; Yan et al., 202; Wang et al., 2024).

Baking Foaming Method with Kraft Lignin

The study by Yan et al. (2021) developed an eco-friendly foaming method for kraft lignin, which is the sole resource. Batches of kraft lignin were dried in the oven at varying temperatures, retaining different levels of moisture. The batches were then subjected to a cold hydraulic press, keeping the moisture inside the lignin blocks. The final step was baking the lignin blocks at a temperature of 10 degrees celsius/minute up to 240 degrees celsius. The moisture inside the blocks acted as the blowing agent, effectively producing an open-celled rigid foam with lignin as the sole resource. This method avoided the use of toxic chemicals that do not break down, as well as petrol-based chemicals that are not sustainable. Its mild processing conditions paired with its sustainability makes it an ideal study to replicate with the goal of reducing negative impact in rigid foam production.

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Water as a chemical and physical blowing agent aided the production of the open-celled structure of the foam. The resultant foams with lower moisture produced denser, smaller, and more uniform foams while higher moisture produced lower density foams with larger and varied pores. In terms of insulation, the lowest conductivity values belong to the foams named LF25, LF50, and LF75. The best resultant foam focusing on thermal insulation is LF25, having the lowest thermal conductivity of 0.030-0.035 W/m*K. The foams with the lowest conductivity values surpass polystyrene foams and are comparable to phenolic-based PUFs. However, the foam with the most uniform structure, higher strength, and mechanical stability but with a slightly higher thermal conductivity is LF125. While this study focuses on thermal insulation, values close to LF125 are used to find a close moisture level due to its mechanical strength fitting for repeating experiments and comparable to conventional insulation foams.

Polyurethane Foams with Lignin as a Partial Polyol

In a study by Alinejad et al. (2019), lignin was discussed as a filler and cross-linking agent in polyurethane foams. Thermal stability and mechanical properties were observed to increase by increasing lignin content. Although in another review by Wang, the 100% replacement of petrol-based polyol with lignin resulted in a dense, brittle, and mechanically weak foam, using a common formulation in flexible foam creation. In another study by Luo et al. (2020), a polyurethane foam with partial replacement of unmodified lignin was created and was shown to exhibit improved compressive properties, thermal stability, and water resistance. Han et al. (2025) produced flexible polyurethane foams with partial lignin substitution and NaCl as a

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medium. The end product provided excellent flexibility, improved cell size (more uniform and smaller), as well as higher resilience and elastic recovery.

While these studies observed improvement in multiple qualities of foams made with lignin, they are all partially infused with petrochemicals as well. Aside from their resistance to biodegradation, some ingredients like isocyanates are toxic, volatile, and pose health risks. Chemicals like TDI and MDI are highly reactive and toxic in their vapor form, fresh foam can auto-ignite during curing, and environmental and health risks are pressing concerns (Ceo, 2025; Bond, 2024).

The study by Yan et al. (2021) used lignin as the sole resource of the foam through environmentally friendly methods via baking and cold press. The most toxic part of their study was kraft lignin, whose process before it becomes kraft lignin (kraft black liquor) is relatively toxic. However, in this study which aimed to replicate the methods of Yan et al. (2021), the DES method was performed instead of kraft lignin utilization, an environmentally friendly approach for extracting lignin. The lignin was derived from the waste bunch of *Arenga pinnata*, an abundant yet underused source of lignin biomass.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1

Schematic Illustration of Key Independent and Dependent Variables Influencing the Thermal Insulation Performance of Arenga pinnata Lignin Foam

The diagram highlights the relationship between the independent and dependent variables, specifically how manipulating the dependent variables influences the thermal performance of the foam samples. This study is conducted within the Chemistry and Biology Laboratory at Lyceum University - Cavite, with a focus on sustainable application.

Definition of Terms

Choline Chloride (ChCl). Choline chloride acts as the hydrogen bond acceptor in the DES solution, promoting the cleavage of lignin bonds and enhancing delignification rate by breaking down the complex lignin polymer into smaller fragments.

Density. Determine the cellular structure compactness of the biocomposite foam. Lower density enhances thermal insulation via higher air entrapment.

Glycerin. A hydrophilic plasticizer of low weight containing polar hydroxyl groups that has the ability to reduce the softening point, improve the flexibility and dispersion of lignin foams.

Lactic Acid. A component of DES solution, acting as a hydrogen bond donor, helps disrupt the lignocellulosic biomass structure by breaking the hydrogen bonds, facilitating lignin solubilization and separation of cellulose and hemicellulose.

Lignin. An aromatic polymer that acts as a glue, holding biomass structures together. It is the main raw material for the resultant foam of the study.

Water. Acts as a physical blowing agent are used in foam manufacturing to produce gas bubbles by physical change (liquid to gas) through evaporation, without undergoing any chemical reaction, and typically at low boiling point. In the study, water moisture acted as the physical blowing agent, which evaporated rapidly and formed steamed bubbles that resulted in typical foam morphology.

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Polyurethane Foam. A lightweight material produced by the expansion of thermoplastic polymer with a blowing agent, commonly used as insulation and packaging due to its durability and moisture resistance. Used as the conventional foam as a point of comparison in the study.

Polyvinyl Acetate. A water-soluble polymer with the ability to film-form, biodegrade, and is biocompatible with lignin-based biocomposites by acting as a stabilizing matrix through hydrogen bonding and consequently enhancing mechanical strength.

Thermal Conductivity. The biocomposite foam's ability to conduct heat; lower values indicate better insulation, as heat flows slowly across the temperature gradient of the foam.

Thermal Resistance. The biocomposite foam's ability to resist heat flow; higher values indicate better insulation by slowing the conduction across temperature differences.

Chapter III

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter includes the detailed methodology of the study. The contents are research design, sample collection, extraction of lignin, formulation process of PUF, insulation tests, and data analysis.

Research Design

This study employed an experimental quantitative research design by manipulating the moisture content in biocomposite lignin foam from *Arenga pinnata* (kaong) using varying water amounts (1.2 mL, 1.4 mL, and 1.6 mL). This design enabled a controlled comparative analysis among biocomposite lignin foams with different water contents and conventional polyurethane foam. The quantitative approach allowed objective measurement of thermal conductivity, resistance and density. Statistical methods were used to analyze differences and relationships observed in the samples, supporting robust and data-driven conclusions.

Process Flow

Figure 2

Flowchart Summary of Pure Lignin Foam Synthesis and Testing.

The flowchart illustrates the step-by-step experimental procedure for extracting lignin from *Arenga pinnata* biomass and preparation of biocomposite lignin-foam along with the statistical test.

Research Locale

This study was conducted at the Biology and Chemistry Laboratory of Lyceum of the Philippines University - Cavite, selected for its well-equipped facilities that are essential for the synthesis and processing required for this study. The laboratory had precise instruments such as analytical balances and graduated cylinders, which were critical for the accurate preparation of

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Deep Eutectic Solvents (DES). Accurate measurements had directly impacted the optimization of lignin yield and adherence with the research timeline. Additionally, magnetic stirrers are used to ensure uniform interaction of reactants, thereby improving lignin extraction efficiency. Other equipment such as temperature-controlled electric ovens, had been essential for evaporating the moisture from the molded lignin – a process necessary for the foam's porous structure formation and better curing of the foam. This step had significantly affected the structural integrity and, consequently, the accuracy of subsequent thermal tests results. Hot plates provided a stable and controlled heating environment necessary for accurate thermal conductivity and resistance testing test results. Together, these facilities had provided the necessary equipment needed for synthesis, thermal testing, and data interpretation, thereby supporting the study's objectives to fill the existing research gaps with reliable and valid results.

Materials and Equipment

The methodology involved several procedures with corresponding equipment. Biomass preparation included sectioning with a kitchen knife and wood saw, followed by pulverization using an electric dry grain pulverizer. The pulverized biomass was sieved using a stainless steel sieve (10 cm diameter with 50 holes per square inch) to ensure uniform particle size. Deep Eutectic Solvents (DES) were prepared by mixing Choline chloride and Lactic acid (personal care grade, with estimated purity of 88 to 90%) using a magnetic stirrer in a 500 mL beaker. For lignin fractionation, an analytical balance (PA214 OHAUS) was used for precise weighing. A magnetic stirrer (CORNING PC-420D) and 500 mL beaker was used in the mixing of DES and biomass; filtration and recovery is performed using distilled water for adjusting of the pH level of DES containing biomass; filter paper and cloth mesh were used to retrieve the lignin, and beaker

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housed the discarded diluted solution. Parchment paper was used for drying the fractionated lignin. Ethanol (70%) was used for lignin characterization. Baking biocomposite foams involved molded foil, silicone cups, spoon, glycerin, polyvinyl acetate (PVA), 1 mL plastic syringe, polvoron molder, starch, hinge cups, and a conduction oven (astron). For the statistical analysis, equipment included a heated plate, digital thermometer, and a ruler.

Sample Collection

Arenga pinnata (kaong) waste was hand picked by a farmer at Indang Cavite. The researchers had obtained the biomass waste from the farmer and had transported it to Lyceum of the Philippines University - Cavite for further processing, which included cleaning, sectioning, drying, and pulverizing into a powder, in preparation for the lignin biocomposite foam.

Sample Preparation

The collected kaong waste was thoroughly washed and subjected to air drying for a duration of 2 days. Following partial removal of moisture, the fruit shell samples were sectioned into smaller pieces using a kitchen knife, while the stalks were sectioned using a wood saw. The soft inner portion of the fruit shell was removed. The remaining rigid shell fragments and sectioned stalk were sun-dried for two consecutive days, after which they were pulverized using an electric dry grain pulverizer. The biomass was subjected to pulverization repeatedly, until finer consistency of biomass was achieved. The resulting pulverized waste materials were sieved to ensure uniform particle size before undergoing lignin fractionation. This process was essential for the mechanical disruption of the bunch and stalk waste, which enhanced the penetration of deep eutectic solvent (DES) mixture. Such disruption facilitates the effective isolation of lignin and supported the subsequent molding of the biocomposite foams.

Preparation of Deep Eutectic Solvents (DES)

Choline chloride (ChCl) acted as the hydrogen bond acceptor and Lactic acid acted as hydrogen bond donor. Both chemicals were obtained from the online shopping platform called Shopee. The DES was prepared in a weight ratio of 1:15 ChCl:LA, respectively. Accordingly, 32.27 g of Choline chloride was accurately weighed using an analytical balance, while 400 mL of Lactic acid was accurately measured using a graduated cylinder. The components were combined in a beaker and stirred using a magnetic stirrer at 80°C with 500 rpm for a duration of 15 minutes, until a homogeneous liquid formed.

Biomass Fractionation using DES

The ratio of pulverized lignin to deep eutectic solvent (DES) employed in this study was 1:9. Accordingly, 44.44 grams of biomass with 50% stalk mixed with 50% fruit shell, was accurately weighed using an analytical balance (OHAUS). The weighed kaong waste was transferred into a beaker, to which 400 mL of the prepared DES was added. The resulting mixture was stirred at 500 rpm for 10 minutes without applying heat and then adjusted to 120 °C and 300 rpm using a magnetic stirrer for a duration of 7 hours and 50 minutes to ensure thorough and uniform interaction of the reactants.

Lignin Filtration and Recovery

After complete dissolution of lignin in deep eutectic solvent (DES) mixture, the residual solid fraction, primarily composed of cellulose, settled at the bottom of the beaker, while lignin remained dissolved in the aqueous phase of the DES. The aqueous portion of the DES mixed with lignin was transferred into another beaker, where lignin precipitation was induced by diluting the lignin-containing DES solution with 500 mL distilled water, adjusting the solution's pH level, thereby creating a concentration gradient within the glass beaker. The mixture was allowed to sit for 30 to 60 minutes to facilitate lignin precipitation. The precipitated lignin was recovered through filtration using a fabric mesh and thoroughly washed using distilled water to remove residual DES and impurities. Finally, filter paper held by a funnel and Erlenmeyer's flask was used to collect the pulverized lignin particles that passed through the fabric mesh.

Drying of Fractionated Lignin

The recovered clustered lignin was sieved to separate the clustered lignin particles collected from filtration, promoting faster drying. The separated lignin was spread out on a parchment paper, which provides a wider surface area and absorbs moisture, enhancing the drying process for a whole day. The use of a parchment paper was preferred to prevent corrosion, as deep eutectic solvent can be highly corrosive to metallic materials. After the lignin was thoroughly dried, one gram of dried lignin was weighed using an analytical balance; this sample was designated for confirmation of lignin identity in the extracted biomass. The lignin was submerged in 30 mL of ethanol (70%), and allowed to incubate at a room temperature for 24 hours. Following the incubation, the residual biomass was collected, dried, and weighed to

confirm the lignin's identity. The results indicated that 45% of the extracted lignin contains ethanol-insoluble biomass, whereas 55% of the original 1 g sample was confirmed as pure lignin.

Preparation of Rigid Biocomposite Foam

Before preparing the lignin, polyvinyl acetate (PVA) was first prepared by dissolving 0.30 g of PVA in 12.3 mL of water in a beaker. The mixture was heated on a hot plate for twenty-one minutes, with the first 5 minutes of heating followed by continuous mixing for the remaining sixteen minutes. Polyvinyl acetate acted as an adhesive for the biocomposite foam, providing enhanced stability and structural integrity. During the initial five minutes, the dry components, which are 3 grams of dried lignin and 1.2 grams of starch were added. The starch contributes to the formation of the foam's porous structure. Subsequently, after the preparation of melted PVA, 1 mL of PVA was added with the dry mixture acting as an adhesive for the rigidity of the structure, along with the 0.9 mL of glycerine, which acted as a plasticizer to improve the foams' flexibility. Additionally, varying moisture contents of 1.2 mL, 1.4 mL, and 1.6 mL were added, contributing with the dimensional stability of the foam. All components were thoroughly mixed using a spoon and silicone cup to ensure homogeneity. The resulting mixture was then shaped using a polvoron molder, and pressed firmly to form a solid structure, effectively entrapping the moisture within the biocomposite foam. Finally, pressed foam was weighed before the baking process then placed into a molded foil. This mold maintained a consistent and controlled environment during curing, while also regulating the pressure and steam released during baking. The baking temperature was ramped from an estimated rate of 5 to 10 °C/min to 230 °C, followed by a holding period of 20 minutes at 230 °C. After baking and cooling, the foam was weighed again; this measurement is essential for subsequent statistical analysis. This entire

process was repeated four times to produce three biocomposite foam samples for each moisture content level and one negative control group.

Density Test

To determine the density of the foam sample, both its mass and volume must be accurately measured. The mass of the foam was obtained using an analytical balance, which provides precise and reliable weight measurements crucial for accurate density calculation. The volume was determined by measuring the height (thickness) of the foam and its cross-sectional area using a ruler. The product of height and area is the volume of the foam sample. Density was then computed by dividing the measured mass by the volume.

The thermal conductivity, thermal resistance, and density of biocomposite foam samples with varying water contents of 1.2 mL, 1.4 mL, and 1.6 mL, along with the control group, were each measured in triplicate manner. To address the research questions outlined in SOPs 1 through 3 regarding the thermal properties of these biocomposite foams, the measurements were processed using specific calculation formulas.

Initially, the cross-sectional area (A) of each foam sample was determined using the formula:

$$r = d/2$$

where d is the diameter of the foam sample, and r is the radius, which was used to compute the area of the biocomposite foams.

Volume was calculated using the formula:

$$V = \pi r^2 h$$

where r is the radius of the circular cross-sectional area, and h is the height of thickness of the foam sample

Thermal Conductivity and Resistance Test

A thin aluminum foil was placed on the hot plate to promote uniform heat distribution. A digital thermometer measured the foam surface temperature directly within the interval time to track the heat passing through the foam and evaluate its thermal conductivity and resistance. Temperature-correlated resistance measurements were recorded after 20 minutes. This procedure was applied on all samples with varying moisture contents, control group, and conventional polyurethane foam. Each was tested three times to ensure statistical confidence in the results. Following the computations from the previous subsection, thermal resistance and conductivity were calculated as follows:

Change in temperature was calculated using the formula:

$$\Delta T = T_{\text{final}} - T_{\text{initial}}$$

where T_{final} is the constant heat plate temperature and T_{initial} is the temperature recorded from each foam sample.

Thermal conductivity (k) was calculated using the formula:

$$k = QL/A\Delta T$$

where Q represents the heat transfer rate, L is the thickness of the foam sample, A is the previously calculated cross-sectional area, and ΔT denotes the temperature difference across the sample.

Thermal resistance (R) was calculated using the formula:

$$R = L/k$$

where L is the foam thickness and k represents the computed thermal conductivity obtained from prior calculation.

Density was calculated using the formula:

$$\rho = m/V$$

where m is the mass (weight) of the foam sample, and V is its volume obtained from prior calculation.

Statistical Treatment and Data Analysis

The computed values of thermal conductivity, thermal resistance, and density were subsequently analyzed using paired t-tests to determine whether significant differences existed among foam samples with varying water contents and the control group. When the p-value obtained from the thermal resistance, conductivity, and density showed less than 0.05, the difference was considered statistically significant, indicating that the thermal properties of kaong biocomposite foams differed from those of polyurethane foam. However, the tests revealed a value greater than 0.05 indicating that there is no significant difference among the biocomposite foams with varying water content and polyurethane foam. This suggests similar performance under the same tested conditions or lack of detectable thermal effects likely stem from small sample size.

Chapter IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents and analyzes the findings of the study aimed at investigating the thermal resistance, conductivity, and density values of DES lignin kaong foams with varying moisture concentrations. The data collected through various experimental procedures are discussed and interpreted to ensure clarity and thorough understanding.

Thermal Resistance Results

Table 1

The Thermal Resistance L/k ($m^2 \cdot K \cdot W^{-1}$) Values of Biocomposite Kaong-Lignin Foams with Varying Water Concentrations

Thermal Resistance	1.2 mL	1.4 mL	1.6 mL	Negative Control	Positive Control
T1	6.19E-05	6.59E-05	6.69E-05	6.60E-05	8.76E-05
T2	6.54E-05	6.84E-05	7.24E-05	7.47E-05	8.91E-05
T3	6.09E-05	7.66E-05	6.90E-05	8.34E-05	8.31E-05
Average	6.272E-05	7.030E-05	6.941E-05	7.471E-05	8.657E-05

Table 1 displays the thermal resistance values for biocomposite kaong-lignin foams with water concentrations of 1.2, 1.4, and 1.6 mL alongside the negative and positive control. Three trials were conducted in order to validate the average result of each differing condition.

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Among the controls, the average thermal resistance was highest for the positive control, followed by the negative control. However, among the experimental foams, the 1.4 mL concentration exhibited the highest value.

With thermal resistance being the quality of foam that reflects how well-equipped it is to resist the flow of heat. Therefore, the higher the thermal resistance value, the better quality foam it is. Through investigating the varying foams, the positive control reflected its superiority in thermal resistance, with the negative control following it. This result suggests the notion that water concentration affects the thermal resistance quality of biocomposite foams.

Among the experimental foams, the 1.4 mL sample showed the highest resistance to heat, possibly due to optimal pore size or formulation. Both higher and lower concentrations produced results that were both lower in thermal resistance, suggesting that variations in pore structure or density affect heat flow in DES lignin biocomposite foams (Jia et al., 2023).

Thermal Conductivity Results

Table 2

The Thermal Conductivity ($W \cdot m^{-1} K^{-1}$) Values of Biocomposite Kaong-Lignin Foams with Varying Water Concentrations

Thermal Conductivity	1.2 mL	1.4 mL	1.6 mL	Negative Control	Positive Control
T1	74.72	106.2	113.1	90.90	102.8
T2	110.6	87.72	107.0	80.35	101.0
T3	101.5	78.30	115.0	83.94	96.35
Average	95.617	90.74	111.69	85.063	100.063

Table 2 displays the thermal conductivity values for biocomposite kaong-lignin foams with water concentrations of 1.2, 1.4, and 1.6 mL alongside the negative and positive control. Three trials were conducted in order to validate the average result of each differing condition.

Among the controls, the average thermal conductivity value was observed to be the least in the negative. In the experimental foams, the sample with the least conductive activity average was 1.4 mL.

Thermal conductivity is defined as the amount of heat a material can conduct, therefore, the lower the conductivity value, the better insulation quality it provides. Within the experimental foams, the least conductive sample was the foam with 1.4 mL water concentration, with an average of 90.74. Including the controls, it exhibited the most desirable thermal conductivity

value. In contrast, the 1.6 mL sample was shown to possess the highest thermal conductivity value with a staggering 111.69, surpassing the positive control. This reflects the value of optimal foam porosity affecting thermal conductivity, which is linked to moisture concentration (Carrico et al., 2017).

Density Results

Table 3

The Density ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) Values of Biocomposite Kaong-Lignin Foams with Varying Water Concentrations

Density	1.2 mL	1.4 mL	1.6 mL	Negative Control	Positive Control
T1	1174	808	906	1011	66.3
T2	714	924	1095	988	58.9
T3	958	892	1098	696	66.3
Average	948.7	874.7	1033	898.3	63.83

Table 2 displays the thermal conductivity values for biocomposite kaong-lignin foams with water concentrations of 1.2, 1.4, and 1.6 mL alongside the negative and positive control. Three trials were conducted in order to validate the average result of each differing condition.

Among the 2 controls, the positive control displayed the least density values, outranking the negative control by a large margin, with the former with an average of 63.83 and the latter with an average of 898.3.

Density as a property of foam is defined as the compactness of mass within a given area, with mass divided by volume. This quality directly impacts insulation, because it quantifies the amount of air trapped within the foam structure, which acts as the primary thermal insulator. Density among the experimental foams was recorded to be lowest in the foam 1.4 mL, with 1.6 being the highest and 1.2 following. Consequently, the sample with the most desirable density quality as foam for insulation purposes was the 1.4 mL, outranking the rest. Density being tightly linked to porosity, which is a direct result of moisture content according to the study of Yan et al. (2024) using similar methodology aligned sensibly with the results (Svantesson, 2021).

Significant Difference on Thermal Resistance

The three trial thermal resistance values of the biocomposite kaong-lignin foam samples were recorded and compared statistically via paired t-test to find out whether or not there's a significant difference in insulating capacity based on moisture. Following the study of Yan et al. (2024) on kraft lignin foams, moisture content was observed to significantly affect porosity, thus, affecting thermal insulation capacity. These findings aligned with their study on eco-friendly lignin foams, linking variations in thermal resistance with porosity, which is linked to moisture concentrations.

Table 4

Significant Difference in the Thermal Resistance Values of Biocomposite Kaong-Lignin Foams with Varying Water Concentrations Compared to Positive Control

Comparison	p-value	Interpretation
1.2 mL	0.002*	Significant
1.4 mL	0.080	Not significant
1.6 mL	0.012*	Significant

p value is significant if <0.05*

As seen in Table 4 only the 1.4 mL concentration was recorded to be not significant compared to the positive control. This indicated that the formulation of moisture samples did not exceed commercial values and that 1.4 mL was statistically insignificant, which could be due to variability in measurements and sample size. Another possibility is the sample does not differ significantly from the positive control under the study conditions. Aside from performing similarly under the same conditions, this could indicate the 1.4 mL sample is comparable to the positive control but equivalence testing or larger sample sizes is further required to validate this assumption (McLeod, 2025).

Table 5

Significant Difference in the Thermal Resistance Values of Biocomposite Kaong-Lignin Foams with Varying Water Concentrations Compared to Negative Control

Comparison	p-value	Interpretation
1.2 mL	0.160	Not significant
1.4 mL	0.178	Not significant
1.6 mL	0.376	Not significant

p value is significant if <0.05*

In Table 5, none of the samples were considered to be statistically different in terms of significance to the negative control. This insignificance compared to the experimental samples, suggests there's an intrinsic insulation capability of unmodified kaong foams. This also suggests the moisture treatment at the selected levels did not statistically enhance or degrade the foam's insulation quality. Additionally, its high thermal resistance in Table 1 indicated the raw kaong foam to be a strong insulator, disregarding the moisture content of PVA glue. This insignificance could also be attributed to their comparability to the negative control foams.

Significant Difference on Thermal Conductivity

The three trial thermal conductivity values of the biocomposite kaong-lignin foam samples were recorded and compared statistically via paired t-test to find out whether or not there's a significant difference in insulating capacity based on moisture.

Table 6

Significant Difference in the Thermal Conductivity Values of Biocomposite Kaong-Lignin Foams with Varying Water Concentrations Compared to Positive Control

Comparison	p-value	Interpretation
1.2 mL	0.744	Not significant
1.4 mL	0.289	Not significant
1.6 mL	0.088	Not significant

p value is significant if <0.05*

For Table 6, none of the formulations were recorded to be statistically significant in terms of thermal conductivity compared to the positive control. Based on the data, the variations in water content were not significant enough to cause a significant change in thermal conductivity relative to the commercial foam. Much like the previous tables, the insignificance could be attributed to their comparability to the positive control.

Table 7

Significant Difference in the Thermal Conductivity Values of Biocomposite Kaong-Lignin Foams with Varying Water Concentrations Compared to Negative Control

Comparison	p-value	Interpretation
1.2 mL	0.526	Not significant
1.4 mL	0.451	Not significant
1.6 mL	0.009*	Significant

p value is significant if <0.05*

As for the Table 7, only the 1.6 mL sample displayed a significant difference compared to the negative control. At this concentration, it can be inferred that this can significantly alter the thermal conductivity of the kaong foam produced compared to the unmodified kaong foam. This change could be attributed to changes in porosity or microstructure caused by moisture level (Yan et al., 2024).

Significant Difference on Density

The three trial density values of the biocomposite kaong-lignin foam samples were recorded and compared statistically via paired t-test to find out whether or not there's a significant difference in insulating capacity based on moisture.

Table 8

Significant Difference in the Density Values of Biocomposite Kaong-Lignin Foams with Varying Water Concentrations Compared to Positive Control

Comparison	p-value	Interpretation
1.2 mL	0.021*	Significant
1.4 mL	0.002*	Significant
1.6 mL	0.004*	Significant

p value is significant if <0.05*

In Table 8, all experimental foams examined were calculated to be statistically different in density values relative to the positive control. This table followed the trend between the density values of the kaong foams, where the experimental density values in Table 3 were tremendous in comparison with the positive control. The significant difference was characteristic of the positive control, the PUF, a foam well-known to be lightweight in nature.

Table 9

Significant Difference in the Density Values of Biocomposite Kaong-Lignin Foams with Varying Water Concentrations Compared to Negative Control

Comparison	p-value	Interpretation
1.2 mL	0.789	Not significant
1.4 mL	0.858	Not significant
1.6 mL	0.456	Not significant

p value is significant if <0.05*

In Table 9, the experimental foams were statistically insignificant compared to the negative control. This highlights the performance of experimental kaong foams being similar under the same conditions with the kaong foams without moisture. Following the trend in the raw weight data, the difference between all the kaong foams including control compared to the PUF aligned with the findings on both density tables. The difference between the two tables both indicate that statistically, experimental foams performed similarly to the negative control foams and aligned closely together, while relative to the positive control, the experimental foams were significantly dense or heavier in measurement (Das & Mahanwar, 2020; Wang, 2019).

Chapter V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATION

This chapter presents the summary, conclusions, and recommendations for future research based on the results obtained from the study's experimental methodology.

Summary of Findings

This study explored an eco-friendly approach of extracting lignin from kaong bunch waste to produce biocomposite foams enhanced with non-toxic additives, including starch, glycerin, and polyvinyl acetate (PVA). The research primarily focused on evaluating the insulating properties, specifically thermal conductivity, thermal resistance, and density of kaong biocomposite foams with varying water content levels (1.2 mL, 1.4 mL, and 1.6 mL). The thermal performance of these biocomposite foams was compared among themselves and against controls 0mL water content (negative control) and conventional polyurethane foam (positive control). This comparative analysis aims to understand how water, as a blowing agent, influences the foam porosity and insulating efficiency. The use of controls provided a benchmark to validate the experimental method and establish the efficacy of the kaong lignin biocomposite foams insulating applications. The biocomposite foam with 1.4 mL water concentration demonstrated the most optimal overall performance among tested samples. It exhibited the highest resistance flow, lower conductivity, and less dense among the tested samples, correlating to better insulating properties.

Conclusion

1. The most thermally resistant experimental foam was 1.4 mL, while the negative control proved superior to all of the kaong foams. The positive control was the most thermally resistant, in line with the expected value of polyurethane foams. This suggests there's an intrinsic insulation capability of DES kaong lignin, and that for moisture foams, 1.4 by average, was the most thermally resistant and most optimal value.
2. The least thermally conductive experimental foam was 1.4 mL, while the negative control was superior to all of the foams tested, including positive control. This suggests there's an intrinsic insulation capability of DES kaong lignin, with 1.2, 1.4, and negative control outperforming the positive control. While the negative control was superior to 1.4, it was still the most thermally resistant and most optimal value among the moisture levels.
3. Among all the kaong foams including the negative control, the least dense sample was 1.4 mL. The positive control outperforms all the foams in terms of density, with its mean value being less than 100 and the kaong foams ranging from 874.7 to 1033. This indicates that the polyurethane foam significantly outperforms DES kaong lignin foams in terms of density, suggesting an area for improvement.
4. In thermal resistance, only the 1.4 mL foam was statistically insignificant compared to the positive control, while all were insignificant compared to the negative foam. This finding suggests the sample does not differ significantly from the positive control under the study conditions, but further testing is required to prove that they are definitely comparable. It could also be attributed to variance in measurement and sample size. Moreover, the selected levels of moisture did not statistically enhance nor degrade the

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foam's insulating quality, and rather indicates that kaong foam is a strong insulator even without additional moisture.

5. In thermal conductivity, none of the foams were significantly different compared to the positive control, while only the 1.6 mL sample was statistically significant compared to the negative control. This finding indicates that the moisture variations were not significant enough to cause significant change in thermal conductivity against the polyurethane foam, while the change in 1.6 mL compared to the negative control could be significant enough to be attributed to moisture level altering porosity.
6. In density, all the foams were statistically different compared to the positive control, while relative to the negative control were all insignificant. This coincides with the fact that polyurethane foam is well known to be lightweight, and the massive numerical difference in density between all kaong foams compared to the positive control can be further observed in the 3rd table. Additionally, this finding suggests that the negative control paired against the experimental foams all performed similarly in terms of density under the same conditions.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are proposed for future researchers who may undertake related studies. These suggestions are attained from the findings of this research, taking into consideration the scope and limitation.

1. Employ standard equipment, a controlled laboratory, and procedures for foam production, baking, and thermal tests (thermal resistance, conductivity, and density). This ensures the accuracy of each variable and condition, lessening error and imprecision that is expected in home laboratory conditions and various alternatives like replacing the laboratory oven with baking oven due to inexpensiveness and availability.
2. Explore a broader range of water concentrations and alternative eco-friendly blowing agents to fine tune foam porosity and optimize insulating properties. This helps expand variance to discover levels with more statistical significance and to further enhance foam morphology and insulation quality.
3. Explore more data, replication, and equivalence testing to confirm superiority. This enables the confirmation of foam comparability or superiority compared to standard foam in terms of insulation and increases accuracy in sample testing.
4. Employ proper testing of purity and enhancing of purity of lignin through proper and improved lignin extraction techniques. Proper testing and extraction with standard protocol mitigates biocomposite limitations in process control, mechanical properties, and density.

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5. Explore the water level contents and additives for the optimization of foam flexibility, durability, and thermal insulation performance. Various levels and specific conditions of each additive may produce a further optimized version of the sample.
6. Compare extraction efficiency and foam quality to other lignin sources. This approach provides context to its performance relative to similarly produced foams, allowing proper evaluation and comparison.

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APPENDICES

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APPENDIX A

Raw Data

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Table 10

Thickness Measurements of Biocomposite Foam Samples with Variable Moisture Contents and Controls

Thickness	1.2	1.4	1.6	Negative control	Positive control (PUF)
1st	0.005	0.007	0.007	0.006	0.009
2nd	0.008	0.007	0.006	0.006	0.009
3rd	0.007	0.007	0.006	0.007	0.008

Table 11

Diameter Measurements of Biocomposite Foam Samples with Variable Moisture Contents and Controls

Diameter	1.2	1.4	1.6	Negative control	Positive control (PUF)
1st	0.031	0.031	0.031	0.032	0.031
2nd	0.032	0.031	0.031	0.033	0.031
3rd	0.031	0.031	0.032	0.035	0.031

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Table 12

The recorded temperature range for biocomposite foams and control groups during statistical test

Temperature	1.2	1.4	1.6	Negative control	Positive control (PUF)
1st	36.7	37.7	36.9	37.7	32.6
2nd	36.5	37.0	36.4	36.9	32.3
3rd	36.3	37.9	35.7	37.0	33.5

Table 13

Dry Weight Result of Biocomposite Foam Samples with Variable Moisture Content and Controls

Dry weight	1.2	1.4	1.6	Negative control	Positive control (PUF)
1ST	4.43	4.27	4.79	4.88	0.45
2ND	4.59	4.88	4.96	5.07	0.40
3RD	5.06	4.71	5.30	4.69	0.40

APPENDIX B
Statistical Analysis Results

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Table 14

The Results of Computed Thermal Conductivity, Resistance, and Density Values.

Group	Trial	$A (m^2)$	$\Delta T (K)$	$k (W \cdot m^{-1} K^{-1})$	$R = L/k$ $(m^2 \cdot K \cdot W^{-1})$	$P (kg \cdot m^{-3})$
1.2	1	0.00075477	13.3	74.72	6.19E-05	1174
1.2	2	0.00080425	13.5	110.6	6.54E-05	714
1.2	3	0.00075477	13.7	101.5	6.09E-05	958
1.4	1	0.00075477	12.3	106.2	6.59E-05	808
1.4	2	0.00075477	13.0	87.72	6.84E-05	924
1.4	3	0.00075477	12.1	78.30	7.66E-05	892
1.6	1	0.00075477	13.1	113.1	6.69E-05	906
1.6	2	0.00075477	13.6	107.0	7.24E-05	1095
1.6	3	0.00080425	14.3	115.0	6.90E-05	1098
Negative Control	1	0.00080425	12.3	90.90	6.60E-05	1011
Negative Control	2	0.00085530	13.1	80.35	7.47E-05	988
Negative Control	3	0.00096211	13.0	83.94	8.34E-05	696
Positive Control	1	0.00075477	17.4	102.8	8.76E-05	66.3
Positive Control	2	0.00075477	17.7	101.0	8.91E-05	58.9
Positive Control	3	0.00075477	16.5	96.35	8.31E-05	66.3

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Table 15

Density Paired T-test Results

Pair/Variables	n	Mean Difference	Standard Deviation	t	df	P (2-tailed)
1.2 vs Positive Control	3	-4.44333	20.59052	-0.374	2	0.744
1.2 vs Negative Control	3	1.0543E1	23.99711	0.761	2	0.526
1.2 vs 1.4	3	4.86667	31.47754	0.268	2	0.814
1.2 vs 1.6	3	1.6093E1	21.10981	1.320	2	0.318
1.4 vs Positive Control	3	-9.31000	6.50247	-1.432	2	0.289
1.4 vs Negative Control	3	5.67667	10.57220	0.930	2	0.451
1.4 vs 1.6	3	2.0960E1	14.97087	2.425	2	0.136
1.6 vs Positive Control	3	1.1650E1	6.43215	3.137	2	0.088
1.6 vs Negative Control	3	2.6636E1	4.43002	10.414	2	0.009

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Table 16

Thermal Conductivity Paired T-test Results

Pair/Variables	n	Mean Difference	Standard Deviation	t	df	P (2-tailed)
1.2 vs Positive Control	3	8.8483E2	226.37812	6.770	2	0.021
1.2 vs Negative Control	3	5.0333E1	285.20928	0.306	2	0.789
1.2 vs 1.4	3	7.4000E1	288.08332	0.445	2	0.700
1.2 vs 1.6	3	8.4333E1	328.06148	0.445	2	0.700
1.4 vs Positive Control	3	8.1083E2	63.02899	22.282	2	0.002
1.4 vs Negative Control	3	-2.366E1	202.53477	-202	2	0.858
1.4 vs 1.6	3	1.5833E2	55.10293	4.977	2	0.038

APPENDIX C
Documentation of Experimental
Procedure

Figure 3

Photo Documentation of Collected Kaong waste at Indang Cavite.

Figure 4

Photo Documentation of Kaong Waste Preparation

Figure 5

Pulverization of Kaong Waste Biomass Using Electric Dry Grain Pulverizer

Figure 6

Preparation of Deep Eutectic Solvents Using Magnetic Stirrer

Figure 7

Lignin Fractionation Using DES Solution

Figure 8

Drying and Filtering of Extracted Lignin

Figure 9

Preparation of Lignin with Additives

Figure. 10

Baking of Biocomposite Foams

Figure 11

Biocomposite Foam with 1.2 Moisture Content Three Trials in Chronological Order Before Baking Process

Figure 12

Biocomposite Foam with 1.4 mL Moisture Content Three Trials in Chronological Order Before Baking Process

Figure 13

Biocomposite Foam with 1.6 mL Moisture Content Three Trials in Chronological Order Before Baking Process

Figure 14

Negative Control Biocomposite Foam Three Trials in Chronological Order Before Baking Process

Figure 15

Biocomposite Foams with 1.2 mL Moisture Content Three Trials in Chronological Order After Baking Process

Figure 16

Biocomposite Foams with 1.4 mL Moisture Content Three Trials in Chronological Order After Baking Process

Figure 17

Biocomposite Foams with 1.6 mL Moisture Content Three Trials in Chronological Order After Baking Process

Figure 18

Biocomposite Negative Control Three Trials in Chronological Order After Baking Process

Figure 19

Photodocumentation of Biocomposite and Polyurethane Foam Thermal Tests

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APPENDIX D

Certificate of Statistical Analysis

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CERTIFICATE OF STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Title of work: Investigating the Thermal Qualities of Biocomposite Lignin Foam

Produced From *Arenga pinnata* (Kaong) Fruit Waste with Non-toxic Additives

This is to certify that this thesis for the degree Bachelor of Science in Biology has been statistically analyzed by the undersigned statistician with respect to appropriate measurement tools and techniques.

ROEL RENZ DEL CALLAR
Statistician

3/27/26

Date Signed

Noted by:

Ms. MARIA LOURDITA P. BOÑGOL
Research Adviser

3/27/26

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APPENDIX E

Certificate of English Editing

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Research Adviser

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